

Charge-Transfer Complexes of 4, 6-Dihalo-1, 3-Dinitrobenzenes with Pyrene

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Charge-transfer complexes of 4,6-dihalo-1,3-dinitrobenzenes with pyrene are prepared and their spectroscopic behaviour have been studied. X-ray evidence is also given.

CHARGE-transfer complexes (C.T.) of aromatic nitro compounds with a variety of donors are widely studied¹⁻⁵. The effect of the introduction of two halogen substituents at 4 and 6 positions into *m*-dinitrobenzene on the formation of C.T. complexes with pyrene forms the subject matter of the present communication.

The preparation of complexes were tried using different solvents like benzene, carbon tetrachloride, etc. Absolute alcohol was found to be a suitable solvent in which we were able to isolate the complexes in a pure state. Thus the complexes of 4,6-dihalo-1,3-dinitrobenzenes with pyrene were obtained as well defined monoclinic needle shaped crystals by mixing the hot saturated ethanolic solutions of donor and acceptor taken approximately in molecular proportions followed by cooling. The complexes were found to be different from either the donor or the acceptor in their crystalline nature, colour, melting point and analysis (Table I). The integral mole ratio was found to be 1 : 1 by elemental analysis. When chromatographed over activated alumina, the individual components were separated.

With excess of the donor, at higher concentrations ($2.3-2.5 \times 10^{-2}M$ donor; $2.9-4.7 \times 10^{-3}M$ acceptor) a slight increase in the intensity of the band at 378 nm was observed in all the three cases. It may be due to masking of the absorption of the donor (pyrene) at 376 nm. Solid state spectra in nujol-mull did not show any absorption band characteristic of a complex. According to Mulliken⁶ the fundamental criterion of a C.T. complex is that there is a characteristic intense absorption band in the electronic spectrum, which is not found in the spectrum of either component. But there are many cases of complexes in which it is experimentally difficult to show the supposed charge-transfer absorption⁷. It may be indicated that these complexes are contact pairs formed by electrostatic forces in addition to Vander Waals forces with little stability in solution. This may also be attributed to the non-planarity of the acceptor molecule caused as a result of introduction of two halo substituents at 4 and 6 positions.

X-ray diffraction studies of the crystals of the complex of 4,6-diiodo-1,3-dinitrobenzene with pyrene, the details of which will be published elsewhere,

TABLE I

4,6-dihalo(x) 1,3-dinitro benzene	Colour of the acceptor	Colour of the donor	Colour and crystalline state of the complex	m.p. (°C) of the complex	C% (Calcd.) Found	H% (Calcd.) Found	N% (Calcd.) Found
1. X = Cl	Pale yellow needles	Colourless solid with yellowish tinge.	Yellow needles	113-14	(60.13) 60.54	(2.73) 2.52	(6.40) 6.78
2. X = Br	Pale yellow stout needles.	-do-	Orange needles	107-8	(50.70) 50.43	(2.27) 2.50	(5.30) 5.12
3. X = I	Golden yellow rods	-do-	Saffron coloured needles.	131-2	(42.44) 42.41	(1.93) 2.21	(4.502) 4.79

When the electronic absorption spectra of the complexes were taken in chloroform and dichloromethane, the observed spectra were found to be only summation spectra of the free components.

reveals that the complex is a single crystal and consists of 1 : 1 ratio of acceptor and donor molecules. The density 2.03 g/cc calculated from X-ray data is in very good agreement with the observed value of 1.99 g/cc determined by floatation method using bromoform and carbon tetrachloride mixture.

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